

WAYS TO HACK Wi-Fi VULNERABILITY NETWORKS

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Abstract: In this article, the main methods of hacking wi-fi networks – vulnerabilities and vulnerability analysis of wireless computer networks, as well as ways and methods of their elimination.

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The above security methods are used to protect against threats of information security violations, these threats can be conditionally divided into two classes:

1. Direct — threats to information security that arise during information exchange over a wireless LAN Wi-Fi;
2. Indirect — threats associated with a large number of Wi-Fi access points

Direct threats

The radio channel within the availability of the Wi-Fi router, with which data is transmitted, is subject to easy interference in order to obtain unauthorized access to resources and information.

The standards governing the operation of Wi-Fi provide for bot authentication and encryption, but these security elements have their flaws and weaknesses.

Encryption affects the speed of data transfer, and it is often disabled by the administrator to optimize traffic in the wireless network. The first Wired Equivalent Privacy encryption standard was discredited by finding vulnerabilities in the RC4 key distribution algorithm.

This slightly slowed down the development of the wireless Wi-Fi network market and caused the creation of the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) group 802.11i to develop a new security standard that takes into account known WEP vulnerabilities, providing 128-bit AES encryption and authentication to protect the transmitted data.

In 2003, the Wi-Fi Alliance presented its vision of this standard, the so-called intermediate version of this standard - Wi-Fi protected access (WPA). Secure Wi-Fi access uses the Temporary key Integrity protocol Temporary Key Integrity Protocol (TKIP).

They also started using the checksum calculation method: MIC (Message Integrity Code), which began to allow checking the integrity of transmitted packets. In 2004, the Wi-Fi Alliance released a new, which has gained great popularity today, the WPA2 standard, which is an improvement on the WPA standard. The main difference between the WPA and WPA2 standards is in the encryption technology: WPA - TKIP and WPA2 – AES. The WPA2 standard allows you to provide a higher level of protection for a wireless network, since TKIP allows you to create keys up to 128 bits long, and AES — up to 256 bits. The threat of blocking information in the Wi-Fi wireless network channel has been practically ignored during the development of wireless network technology. Channel blocking is not dangerous, because usually wireless Wi-Fi networks are auxiliary to wired networks, despite the fact that blocking can be a preparatory stage for a man-in-the-middle attack, when a third device is introduced

between the router and the client device, redirecting traffic between the router and the client through itself.

This implementation allows you to delete, modify information in different ways, as well as "slip" false information.

Outsiders

Outsiders (Rogue Devices, Rogues) are peripheral devices and computers that provide the possibility of unauthorized access to the corporate network, usually bypassing the protective mechanisms defined by the security policy.

A ban on any use of wireless communication devices will not be able to protect against wireless network attacks if a stranger appears on the network, intentionally or unintentionally.

Anything that has wired and wireless interfaces can act as an alien device: routers (including software), projectors, scanners, laptops with both interfaces enabled, etc.

The unfixed nature of communication

Wireless Wi-Fi devices can easily change the connection points to the network right in the process of operation and even unnoticed by the user. For example, "random associations" may occur when a laptop with Windows XP ((configured to trust all wireless networks) or 19just an incorrectly configured wireless network client automatically associates and connects the user to the nearest wireless Wi-Fi network.

Thus, an attacker can switch a user to his fake access point for subsequent vulnerability scanning, phishing, or man-in-the-middle attacks. And if the user device is connected to a wired LAN at the same time, then it becomes an entry point, so-called strangers.

In addition to this, many users connected to an internal LAN using a Wi-Fi interface, usually dissatisfied with the quality and policy of the network, switch to the nearest available access point (or a negligently configured operating system does this automatically when a wired network fails). At the same time, all the built network protection fails. There is another problem — point-to-point networks, with which it is convenient to transfer files between colleagues or print on a printer that supports Wi-Fi. But such an organization of wireless networks does not support many security methods, which makes them easily accessible prey for an attacker. And the new technologies that have come Virtual Wi-Fi and Wi-Fi Direct have only worsened the security situation.

Vulnerabilities of networks and devices incorrectly configured network devices, devices with weak and insufficiently long encryption keys, using compromised authentication methods — these are the devices that are attacked in the first place. "According to analysts' reports, most of the successful hacks occur precisely because of incorrect settings of access points and client software." [3]

Incorrectly configured access points

It is necessary to connect an incorrectly configured access point to the network to hack the latter. The factory settings, the so-called "default", usually do not include encryption and authentication, or use the keys prescribed in the user manuals, and therefore they are well-known even on the official forums of the manufacturer.

It is unlikely that users are seriously puzzled by the configuration of devices aimed at security. It is these brought wireless access points that create the main threats to protected networks.

Incorrectly configured wireless clients

Incorrectly configured client devices are a much more dangerous threat than incorrectly configured access points. These are client devices, and they are usually not configured specifically for the security of an enterprise's internal network.

In addition, they are usually located outside the perimeter of the controlled area or inside the perimeter, which can allow an attacker to carry out all kinds of attacks, for example, to distribute virus software or simply provide an easily accessible and convenient entry point.

Breaking encryption

The security of the compromised WEP security algorithm is out of the question. The Internet has freely available special and easy-to-use software for hacking this standard, which collects traffic statistics until it becomes sufficient to restore the encryption key.

The WPA and WPA2 standards also have several vulnerabilities of varying degrees of danger that allow them to be hacked, but there is no information yet about successful attacks on WPA2-Enterprise (802.1x).

Impersonation and Identity Theft

Impersonation (impersonating another person) of an authorized user is a serious threat to any computer network, this applies not only to wireless.

However, in a wireless network, it is more difficult to determine the authenticity of a user. There are SSIDs and attempts can be made to filter by MAC addresses, but both are transmitted over the air in open form, and it is not difficult to fake them, and when you fake them, you can at least reduce the network bandwidth by inserting the wrong frame, and a little understanding of the algorithms 21 encryption, arrange penetration testing into the entire network structure (for example, use ARP-spoofing attacks).

Impersonation of the user is possible not only in case of substitution of the MAC address with MAC authentication installed or using static keys. Networking schemes based on 802.1x (WPA2 Enterprise) are not absolutely secure. Some mechanisms (LEAP) have a hacking complexity similar to WEP hacking. Other mechanisms, EAP-FAST or PEAP MSCHAPv2, although more reliable, do not guarantee resistance to a complex attack carried out by an attacker.

Denial of service

DoS attacks are aimed at disrupting the quality of functioning of the wireless network service or at absolute termination of user access and equipment failure before reboot. In the case of a Wi-Fi network, it is very difficult to track the source flooding the network with "garbage" packets specific to this type of attack

— Its location is limited only by the coverage area. In addition, there is a hardware version of this attack — the installation of a sufficiently strong source of interference in the frequency range of a working access point, the so-called "jammers".

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